

Seismic reflection images and explanations

Data from: Deformed submarine terraces in Puget Sound, USA indicate only one $M > \sim 7.5$ earthquake on the Seattle fault zone in the past 11,000 years

Elizabeth J. Davis, Juliet G. Crider, Ralph A. Haugerud, Emily Roland, Ginevra Moore

Figure 1. Tracks of a 2019 CHIRP seismic reflection survey offshore Bainbridge Island. Green lines show survey path; white highlight shows the line segment shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. CHIRP seismic reflection line from 2019 survey that crosses a submerged terrace. Annotations show interpretations of seismic reflectors. Pink circles show the locations that were picked as the buried inner edge and the corresponding bathymetric shoreline angle, which is seaward. The difference in depth between these two picks is 1 m.

Figure 3. Annotated photo of print map showing track lines (black dotted lines) in Elliott Bay from the survey by R/V Onar 1001 in April, 1982. Individual streets in Seattle are identifiable, as well as depth contours (solid black lines). Track lines and shot points are numbered and link map locations to seismic images. The yellow highlight denotes line 1-3; the red circle denotes shot point 0946 (shown in Figure 4). The unpublished paper files located at the Department of Oceanography at the University of Washington.

Shot points, numbered, correspond to map in S

The full dataset of seismic reflection lines cover much of Elliott Bay.

Figure 4. Annotated photo of minisparker seismic reflection line from the survey by R/V Onar 1001 in April 1982 that crosses a submerged terrace offshore Magnolia (Location in Figure S3.4). This is part of line 1-4 collected by the R/V Onar. Shot points are labeled along the top of the photo. Pink circles annotate where we interpreted the back and inner edges of a submerged terrace. The difference between these depths is 3 m. The unpublished paper files are stored at the Department of Oceanography at the University of Washington.